

Policy for Assigning Persistent Identifiers (PIDs) in BBMRI-ERIC

Preamble

Definition of terms:

- *Persistent/persistence* - long-term preservation “for eternity” (practical limitations may occur, e.g., when the whole organization is terminated without a successor)
- *Persistent Identifier (PID)* - any identifier assigned with requirement for persistency
- *Non-reassignable/non-reassignability* - the fact that the same identifier can not be reassigned to another object after the original object user with this identifier was destroyed or got out of existence.
- *Traceability* - ability to figure out history of an object, in case of BBMRI-ERIC biological material and/or data
- *Repeatability* - ability to repeat one’s own research results
- *Reproducibility* - ability to reproduce research results by other researchers
- *BBMRI-ERIC Directory* - a findability service¹ for biobanks and their collections of biological samples and data, maintained by BBMRI-ERIC.
- *Provenance information* - information documenting history of the object.

Use of PIDs in BBMRI-ERIC

Purpose

The PIDs are used in BBMRI-ERIC to identify several types of objects that are expected to be used in various contexts:

- identifiers of biobanks,
- identifiers of collections of biological samples and data (typically inside biobanks),
- identifiers of sets of biological samples used in research,
- identifiers of data sets used in research,
- identifiers of individual biological samples.

The PIDs are used for several main purposes (this list is not exclusive):

- Traceability of biological material and data in biobanks by maintaining findable and accessible

¹ <https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/>

- provenance information describing retrieval, processing, and storage of biological samples,
- provenance information describing retrieval and processing of data.
- Reproducibility of research results by publishing PIDs of biological samples and data (or sets of these) used to obtain research results, linked to findable and accessible provenance information.
- Citation of bioresources (biobanks/collections) to give credits to service providers used in the given research.

Types of PIDs used in BBMRI-ERIC

There are two sources of PIDs anticipated in the BBMRI-ERIC ecosystem at the time of writing this policy, but the policy should be applicable to any sources of PIDs (and possibly extended to accommodate them if needed).

DOIs provided by DataCite consortium, used globally for identifying various objects, most commonly used for identifying published research results (papers). The application of BBMRI-ERIC to DataCite is pending, as the annual cost is substantial and there has to be consensus on their use.

ePIC PIDs provided by European Persistent Identifier Consortium². The advantage is that these identifiers must be resolvable but not necessarily to web pages, plus they are more affordable than DOIs.

Rules for PIDs in BBMRI-ERIC

Example for an ePIC PID

ePIC PIDs are resolvable by
<http://hdl.handle.net>

An ePIC PID consists of a prefix, which denotes the administrative domain and the owner of the PIDs. Prefixes are unique in the whole Handle domain (like DNS domains). The prefix is extended with suffixes which need to be unique for their prefix:

21.T12995/b9ec956a-0ee4-11e7-a912-04040a64000d

Here 21.T12996 is the prefix.

In general the data behind a PID is directly resolvable if accessible by the HTTP protocol.
 E.g. (Example will download a small csv file from a tutorial)

<http://hdl.handle.net/21.T12995/b9ec956a-0ee4-11e7-a912-04040a64000d>

² <http://www.pidconsortium.eu/>

The metadata registered with the PID is called the PID (or in that case the Handle) record. You can inspect the Handle record with:

<http://hdl.handle.net/21.T12995/b9ec956a-0ee4-11e7-a912-04040a64000d?noredirect>

The very first key-value pair gives the data location.

At index 100 these PIDs contain an entry on accession rights.

You can also define other key-value like in index 2 (TYPE) and you can link to other objects via PIDs as done in index 3 which points to another file, which is kept on a local computer and thus not directly reachable via the PID. However, the link between the two data files and their relationship and ownership can be kept and made accessible via the Handle system.

General PID Assignment Principles

- Assignment of PIDs can be done on BBMRI-ERIC level, or a BBMRI-ERIC National Node may request a prefix assigned by BBMRI-ERIC (free of charge) and delegate assignment of PIDs to the National Node level.
- BBMRI-ERIC is responsible for maintaining infrastructure necessary to resolve PIDs assigned on BBMRI-ERIC level and to forward resolve queries for prefixes assigned to National Node.
- If assignment is delegated to a BBMRI-ERIC National Node by having a prefix assigned, it is the responsibility of that National Node to maintain infrastructure to resolve the assigned PIDs persistently. BBMRI-ERIC will only link to this service for resolving given prefix.
- PID assignment and resolving must comply with the requirements of given PID type.

Assigning PIDs for Biobanks and Collections

- PIDs are automatically assigned to all BBMRI-ERIC associated biobanks, either on the level of BBMRI-ERIC or a National Node
 - The assignment must be done no later than as a part of publishing data on the given biobank in BBMRI-ERIC Directory. Transitional period applies from the time this policy is published for the first time - 3 months period is granted to assign the PIDs retrospectively to biobanks already published in the BBMRI-ERIC Directory.
 - The PIDs are reported in the BBMRI-ERIC Directory, which also provides capability to map between different types of identifiers (persistent or not) for the given biobank.
 - If a biobank ceases to exist, the PID must be maintained based on the last state of the biobank, together with the date of termination of operation of the biobank. If the biobank is merged with other biobank, the PID must be maintained for the original biobank and also link to the PID of the biobank with was merged with (the new “merged” biobank is supposed to receive a new PID to avoid confusion).

- PIDs are assigned to collections of biological material and data in BBMRI-ERIC associated biobanks per request of (a) National Node, or (b) the parent biobank, or (c) the responsible person for that collection.
 - The PIDs are reported in the BBMRI-ERIC Directory, which also provides capability to map between different types of identifiers (persistent or not) for the given collection.

Assigning PIDs to Sets of Biological Samples and/or Data Sets Released for Research

- A PID shall be assigned to each set of biological samples or data that was released by a biobank (or BBMRI-ERIC in exceptional cases when BBMRI-ERIC becomes custodian of some data) for a research purpose.
 - On the level of BBMRI-ERIC, the PID shall resolve to a PID of the biobank that released the set.
 - The biobank is responsible for persistent storage of mapping the PID to the samples and data elements constituting the set for reproducibility reasons. The PID mapping must include timestamp of the mapping to the data elements, if the data set is mutable.
- PID of a set of individual samples must be resolvable inside the biobank to complete provenance information about retrieval, processing, and storage of each contributing sample.
- PID of a set of data must be resolvable inside the biobank to complete provenance information about retrieval and processing of the data that lead to creation of the data set.
- When applied to data sets, this “PID on release” policy applies only to those data sets that are released per-request, i.e., publicly and/or persistently available data sets are handled by a separate policy below.

Assigning PIDs to Individual Samples

The policy for assigning PIDs to individual samples is tentative and subject to further discussion in the community due to the cost this would create for the biobanks.

- A PID is recommended (but not required) to be assigned to each sample in the BBMRI-ERIC associated biobank.
 - On the BBMRI-ERIC level, the PID shall resolve to the PID of the biobank hosting the sample.
 - The biobank is responsible for persistent storage of PIDs assigned to samples for reproducibility reasons.

- PID of individual samples must be resolvable inside the biobank to complete provenance information about retrieval, processing, and storage of the sample.
- This policy for individual samples is only possible using PIDs that support the scale of 10^{12} identifiers (DOI PIDs are not recommended for this purpose).

Assigning PID to Published Data Sets

- A PID shall be assigned to each set publicly and/or persistently available data set.
- If the data set is mutable, versioning must be used and either included in PIDs (if supported by the given type of PIDs), or individual PID must be assigned to each version of the data set.
- Each data set PID resolution must include PID of the custodian of the data set (typically a biobank in the context of BBMRI-ERIC, but other institutions may also publish derived data sets). If the custodian is a BBMRI-ERIC associated biobank, the must be resolvable in the BBMRI-ERIC Directory.

Assigning PIDs for BBMRI-ERIC Publications

- Official BBMRI-ERIC Publications shall be assigned a DOI.
 - This can be done by one of the free services such as Zenodo³.

Giving Credits to Bioresources and Data Citation Principles

- BBMRI-ERIC endorses use of BRIF/CoBRA principles⁴ for citations use of bioresources.
- BBMRI-ERIC endorses Force11 DC¹ data citation principles⁵.

Related Standard / Initiatives

ISO/IEC, ITU-T Object Identifiers (OID)

- **OID** is an identification mechanism for naming any type of object, concept or "thing" with a globally unambiguous name which requires a persistent name (long life-time). OIDs, once allocated, should not be re-used for a different object/thing. OIDs are based on a hierarchical name structure, the "OID tree". <http://oid-info.com/index.htm>
EC has the ID 1.3.130 which is iso(1)-identified-organisations(3)-european-commission(130)
BBMRI-ERIC could e.g. be 1.3.188 => iso(1)-identified-organisations(3)-bbmri-eric(188)
and assign further subcodes in the tree.
Most populated arcs in the oid tree: <http://oid-info.com/density.htm>

³ <https://zenodo.org/>

⁴ Bravo E, Calzolari A, De Castro P, *et al.* [Developing a guideline to standardize the citation of bioresources in journal articles \(CoBRA\)](#). *BMC Medicine* 2015;13:33 (doi: 10.1186/s12916-015-0266-y)

⁵ <https://www.force11.org/datacitation>

FHIR/HL7

- HL7 OID registry <https://www.hl7.org/oid/>
- HL7 EI - Entity Identifier <http://www.hl7.eu/refactored/dtEI.htm>
- HL7 HD - Hierarchic Designator <http://www.hl7.eu/refactored/dtHD.html>

Clinical Trials

- Element Identifiers of the CDISC Operational Data Model (ODM) and OpenClinical OIDs https://www.cdisc.org/system/files/all/generic/application/octet-stream/odm1_3_0_final.htm#toc12

Medicine (non research) / organ transplants / blood donors

- ISBT128 standard for the identification, labeling, and information transfer of medical products of human origin (including blood, cells, tissues, milk, and organ products) <https://www.iccbba.org>
- SEC Single European Code for tissues and cells https://ec.europa.eu/health/blood_tissues_organ/tissues/single_european_code_en

Global Unique Patient Identifiers / RD

- Global Rare Diseases Patient Registry Data Repository GUID, <https://ncats.nih.gov/grdr/guid> http://www.rare-diseases.eu/wp-content/uploads/2013/08/91_t2.pdf

Name service for Internet resources

- **Domain Name System (DNS)** - DNS names are typically managed by the network administrator(s) at the DNS zone level. There is no provision for per-name administrative structure and no facilities for anyone other than the network administrator to create or manage DNS names. This is appropriate for domain name administration, but less so for general-purpose resource naming.
- **Handle System** - technical base to DOIs and ePIC Identifiers.
- **Directory Services (X.500/LDAP)** - The fundamental difference between a Handle System, and a directory service such as LDAP, is the search capability. Directory services may be used in tandem with the Handle System to provide reverse lookup service.
- **URNs** were conceived as **persistent**, usually **opaque** or at least location-independent, identifiers assigned within defined **namespaces**, typically by an authority responsible for the namespace, so that they are globally unique and persistent over long periods of time, even after the resource which they identify ceases to exist or becomes unavailable, e.g.
`urn:nbn:de:bvb:19-146642`
A National Bibliography Number for a document, indicating country (de), regional network (bvb = Bibliotheksverbund Bayern), library number (19) and document number.
For URNs locations are assumed to be independent of names. URN resolution is still an active topic of discussion, which requires (1) a formal registration process as a urn namespace, and

(2) accompanying specifications to implement a series of functional requirements for such namespaces.

Bioinformatics / Elixir

- LSID is a (URN) urn:lsid:<Authority>:<Namespace>:<ObjectID>[:<Version>]
There has been a lot of interest in LSIDs in the bioinformatics community, today this project seem to be dead. <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/LSID>
- MIRIAM - Persistent identification for life science data <http://www.ebi.ac.uk/miriam/>
- Identifiers.org is also a resolving system, that relies on collections listed in the MIRIAM Registry <http://identifiers.org>